

A NEW SYNTHESIS OF 2-METHYLPHENANTHRENE

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Ethyl 3-methylcyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate has been condensed with benzyl chloride in the presence of sodium ethoxide to yield ethyl α -cyano- α -(3-methylcyclohexenyl)- β phenylpropionate (I) which on cyclisation, followed by hydrolysis and dehydrogenation, furnishes 2-methylphenanthrene.

We needed 2-methylphenanthrene for our investigation on Friedel-Crafts' reaction (*Science & Culture*, 1947, 12, 410; 1948, 14, 40). Although various methods have been recorded in literature for its synthesis, the above compound was prepared following the method of Ganguli (*ibid.*, 1941-42, 7, 319) for the synthesis of phenanthrene derivatives.

Ethyl 3-methylcyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate was condensed with benzyl chloride in the presence of sodium ethoxide in ethanol solution according to the procedure of Cope *et al.* (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 60, 2903) to yield ethyl α -cyano- α -(3-methylcyclohexenyl)- β phenylpropionate (I) as a viscous liquid.

The cyclisation of (I) was effected with concentrated sulphuric acid and the cyclised product was hydrolysed *in situ* by the addition of aqueous acetic acid (1:1) and refluxing for thirty five hours. A gummy acid was isolated which did not decolorise bromine in carbon tetrachloride solution and was converted into its methyl ester by

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refluxing with methanol and concentrated sulphuric acid. Hydrolysis of the above ester did not yield any crystalline acid, and other means to induce crystallisation also failed. It is possible that the gum represents a mixture of structural (IIa, III) and steric isomers. However, the acid could be converted into its anilide and a homogeneous product of m.p. 199° was isolated in 58% yield.

The gummy acid was then dehydrogenated with selenium without further purification and the resulting product was directly converted into its picrate; on crystallisation from methanol (five times) the product melted at $117-18.5^{\circ}$ (Haworth, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1125, records m.p. $118-19^{\circ}$).

2-Methylphenanthrene (IV) was isolated from the above picrate by treatment with dilute ammonia solution, which after crystallisation from 95% ethyl alcohol melted alone or mixed with an authentic specimen at 55° .

The formation of a homogeneous anilide in fairly good yield and isolation of only 2-methylphenanthrene from the dehydrogenation experiment indicate that (IIa) represents the major portion of the product obtained on ring-closure and hydrolysis.

EXPERIMENTAL

Ethyl α -Cyano- α -(3-methylcyclohexenyl)- β -phenylpropionate (I).—Ethyl 3-methylcyclohexylidene-cyanoacetate (64.5 g.) after cooling for half an hour in an ice and salt bath was added to a sodium ethoxide solution (from 7.3 g. of sodium and 225 c.c. of dry ethanol), also cooled for the same period in a similar manner. The mixture thus obtained was cooled for further 45 minutes with occasional shaking. Benzyl chloride (42 g.) was then added to it and the reaction mixture was immediately transferred on a boiling water-bath and refluxed for 6 hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and extracted with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate, the ether was removed and the product was distilled in vacuum, b.p. $185^{\circ}/3$ mm., yield 80 g. (86%). (Found: N, 4.86. $C_{15}H_{23}O_2N$ requires N, 4.71 per cent).

2-Methylphenanthrene (IV).—Cold concentrated sulphuric acid (48 c.c.) was added to the above ester (30 g.) cooled in iced water. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for 12 hours and then refluxed for 35 hours with the addition of glacial acetic acid (72 c.c.) and water (72 c.c.). Water was added and the mixture was extracted thoroughly with ether. The acidic material was isolated by washing the ethereal solution with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution, followed by acidification. The crude gummy material was esterified with methanol (100 c.c.) and concentrated sulphuric acid (d 1.84, 6 c.c.) by refluxing for 18 hours. The product was worked up by dilution with iced water and extraction with ether. The ether extract was washed with water, dilute sodium carbonate solution and water successively and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. After removing the ether, the residue was distilled in vacuum, b.p. $180^{\circ}/6$ mm., yield 8 g. (Found: C, 78.89; H, 8.59. $C_{17}H_{23}O_2$ requires C, 79.07; H, 8.52 per cent).

The above ester (6 g.) was hydrolysed by refluxing with caustic potash (3 g.) in methanol (26 c.c.) for 4 hours. After removal of the methanol the residue was dissolved in water and the neutral matter was extracted with ether. The aqueous solution was

acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid and the gummy acid was extracted with ether. From the ether solution the acid was extracted with dilute sodium bicarbonate solution and was obtained again as a gum on re-acidification. The product was then purified by distillation in vacuum, b.p. $210^{\circ}/4$ mm., yield 4 g.

Preparation of the Anilide.—Thionyl chloride (1.2 c.c.) and one drop of pyridine were added to a solution of the above acid (2 g.) in dry ether (10 c.c.), cooled in ice water and left as such for 2 hours with occasional swirling. Ether and excess of thionyl chloride were removed under diminished pressure at 55° - 60° . The viscous residue was dissolved in thiophene-free benzene (10 c.c.) and cooled in ice water and to it was added slowly a solution of aniline (4 g.) in chloroform (25 c.c.). The reaction mixture was treated with water and the organic layer separated and thoroughly washed with water. Solvents were removed and the anilide was obtained as a crystalline residue. Crystallisation from petroleum ether and then from methanol yielded a product of constant m.p. 199° , yield 1.5 g. (58% of the theory). (Found: N, 4.94. $C_{13}H_{15}ON$ requires N, 4.4 per cent).

The above acid (2 g.), purified by distillation, and selenium (8 g.) were heated in a metal-bath at 290° - 300° for 24 hours and then at 300° - 315° for another 24 hours. The product was extracted with benzene, filtered from excess of selenium and dried. After removal of the benzene the residue was heated with a little sodium at 150° - 160° for 15 minutes.

The mixture was cooled, extracted with benzene and the residue distilled after removal of the solvent. The oily distillate was converted into its picrate by treating with a saturated solution of picric acid in ethanol. The picrate after several crystallisations (five times) from methanol was collected as orange-yellow crystals, which melted at 117 - 118.5° (mixed m.p. with picric acid, m.p. 121° , was checked and a depression was observed).

2-Methylphenanthrene was regenerated from the picrate with dilute ammonia solution and was purified by crystallisation from 95% ethyl alcohol, m.p. 55° . The mixed melting point with an authentic specimen of 2-methylphenanthrene showed no depression.

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